

Key Factors of Elected Representative Candidate Image Management: A Case of Taiwan Election

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Abstract

In contemporary times, voter awareness has increased, and information circulates more rapidly, intensifying electoral competition. A review of the literature reveals that much of the existing research has explored "party identification" or "the impact of traditional media on electoral campaigns", with scant attention given to the candidates' personal images. However, as times change, the influence of party identification has waned, supplanted by the "candidate image" as a critical factor in voter decision-making. This study synthesizes five dimensions from past literature—family background, personal traits, party identification, electoral strategies, and media relations—along with 23 influencing criteria under these dimensions and proposes an evaluation framework for "candidate image" following an expert survey. This paper employs DEMATEL-based ANP (DANP) to explore the key criteria affecting candidate image, initially using DEMATEL to calculate the interrelationships among the criteria, then applying ANP to ascertain the precise weights of each criterion. Finally, it incorporates Importance Performance Analysis (IPA) to create a performance evaluation chart, determining the management approaches for each criterion. The research findings indicate a consensus among legislators and their staff on the importance of media image and political experience as key criteria, hoping to offer pertinent recommendations for political practitioners and emerging scholars.

Keywords

candidate image; election strategy; Decision-Making Trial and Evaluation Laboratory (DEMATEL); Analytic Network Process (ANP); Importance Performance Analysis

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Introduction

Voter awareness has increased substantially in Taiwan in recent years, with the voting tendencies of young people playing a pivotal role. The slogan “Choose the person, not the party” can frequently be seen during election periods, which suggests that the image of a candidate should be more important to voters than their political party. Voters are no longer supporting candidates based solely on their party affiliation; instead, they are meticulously evaluating the image and qualifications of candidates to ascertain their suitability to their position. Thus, the image that a candidate projects, as well as their family background, profession, class representation, political involvement, media exposure, and interaction with social media followers, has become an important factor that voters consider. Constructing an image that meets the requirements of the aforementioned aspects is crucial for candidates to win in an election.

A candidate’s image encompasses their perception and impression of society and social issues, as well as the appearance that they cultivate to gain voter recognition and votes. Research on the image of Taiwanese candidates indicated that voters heavily weigh candidates’ character and image, such as their achievements, virtues, and demeanor, as primary voting considerations, with up to 70% placing significant emphasis on such factors. Contemporary election studies also revealed that candidates’ abilities, such as knowledge, intelligence, efficiency, leadership, interpersonal skills, virtues, and honesty (Cheng et al., 2005), are vital image factors valued by modern voters. Historically, political scientists believed that party identification plays a dominant role in voting behavior. However, recently, political communication scholars have underscored the importance of candidates’ charisma or image. Voters have focused increasingly on candidate-related factors, instead of party affiliation, with the idea behind the “Choose the person, not the party” slogan becoming a primary consideration in their voting decisions. In critical elections, a candidate’s image and charisma can significantly influence voters’ behavior.

The concept of “image” may have emerged later in election-related academic research than in studies on party or political issues, but in the practical election process, voters gather information about the election and candidates through the media and social media, which can shape their preferences and impression. Extensive research on candidates’ image has been conducted domestically and internationally. For instance, Miller et al. (1986) analyzed American voters’ five-point candidate-centered image assessments, and Chen (1992) categorized voters’ perception of candidates into character, knowledge, approach to tasks, helpfulness, ability to secure local development, welfare for the people, and empathy in serving voters and identified the factors as critical indicators for evaluating the candidates’ image. Chen (2000) examined and classified 10 candidate traits and concluded that a candidate’s image consists of seven politically related aspects, namely, problem-solving ability, leadership, integrity, trustworthiness, ability to meet public needs, international outlook, and efficiency, and three politically unrelated aspects, namely, charm, approachability, and leadership temperament. Cheng (2014) and Chen (2015a) demonstrated that a candidate’s image is a subjective perception held by voters, who use image models to select the best candidates. Party preference and governance performance can also influence voters’ choices. Chou et al. (2017) pointed out that democratic politics is a competitive process, in which political elites use various means to establish their candidate image to garner votes. Wang (2000) asserted that the media exerts a substantial impact on Taiwanese voters, particularly in relation to image construction. Lin (2001) noted that the concept of “candidate image” is a fusion of many factors and not limited to a single trait, including personal characteristics, appearance, education, life experience, political experience, issue preference, and media coverage, which contribute to its conceptual formation.

This study finds that the personality traits exhibited by candidates have evolved, and the focus of media attention has shifted accordingly. Modern candidates who possess distinct personal characteristics and images tend to attract the favor of the media and voters. For example, in Taiwan's 2022 mayoral elections and 2024 presidential elections, the candidates and the public increasingly prioritized various social media platforms and extensively used tools such as Facebook, LINE, and YouTube for election promotion and personal image creation. So-called "social media managers" have become integral members of campaign teams, who employ diverse copywriting and campaign slogans to garner media and voter attention and seek wide coverage. The goal of candidates is to win in elections through effective social media promotion (Chen, 2020).

Historically, voters learn about candidates and get election news from traditional newspapers and television; however, such channels have gradually evolved into various social media platforms. Over time, and with the advancement of technology, public office candidates have enhanced their promotional and software skills to align with voters' usage habits and utilized the most convenient methods to ensure that their messages reach voters. Therefore, new media has become one of the most essential strategies used by candidates in their campaigns.

As voters' decision-making awareness changes, reevaluating their image positioning to identify the traits that meet the expectations of modern voters has become necessary for candidates. Candidate image factors are broad, and their content and communication media are evolving; thus, this study aims to explore how voters in this fast-paced information era identify image factors connected with their experiences that can influence the formation of their perception of and preference for candidates. Identifying the type of candidate image that will have the most influence in future elections is crucial. Campaign teams can leverage their candidate's characteristics to shape their image that will resonate with voters to secure voter support and achieve election victory.

In view of this aim, the research objectives of this study are as follows: (1) To establish an evaluation framework for candidate image construction; (2) To explore the key factors that can influence the construction of a candidate's image and their interrelationships; (3) To provide a strategic reference to candidates for constructing their image.

To comprehend the current standards by which voters perceive candidates' image and the key factors that can influence their voting choices, this study constructs a theoretical framework based on candidate evaluations, voting behavior theory, and political marketing theory. This study conducts a comprehensive review of the literature on candidates' image to explore its definition and implications. Subsequently, this study performs a theoretical analysis of candidates' image, which is pertinent to the research topic. Specifically, this study aims to elucidate the relationship between voters' perception of a candidate's image and their voting behavior by conducting qualitative interviews and questionnaire surveys with political practitioners, representatives, and academic experts in the country.

Then, this study analyzes the data collected from the interviews and materials to examine the positive relationship between voters' perception of candidates based on different image dimensions and their voting behavior. The analysis can inform the development of image-shaping and political marketing strategies. This study also categorizes various interaction scenarios to deduce the optimal marketing technique combinations and strategies for enhancing a candidate's favorability. Such strategies aim to improve voters' perception of candidates, garner maximum voter support, and provide political practitioners with critical insights for campaign strategy formulation.

The primary research methods employed in this study are the Decision-Making Trial and Evaluation Laboratory (DEMATEL) and Analytic Network Process (ANP) techniques. This research focuses on current representatives and related political practitioners and examines five major

dimensions: family background, personal traits, party affiliation, election strategies, and media relations. The dimensions are further subdivided into 23 criteria to measure the candidates' performance in each aspect. This study seeks to understand how a candidate's performance in the aspects can influence their image construction and identify the key factors that can influence, as well as the causal relationship between, voters' preference and voting behavior. By analyzing the candidates' performance in the different dimensions, this study can inform future campaign teams in their formulation of effective election strategies.

Literature review

The concept of candidate image

Image can be defined as a perception formed through the interaction of subjective consciousness and objective concepts. Subjectively, under specific experiential conditions, an individual will project a certain appearance or adopt a particular attitude to make an impression on others, who in turn will internalize the appearance or attitude to form a perception of the individual. In ancient China, the term "image" connoted "representation", which refers to a replication or an imitation of a person or an object. Thus, an image may resemble or be identical to an actual situation but can also differ from the meaning represented by an actual object. Discourse mentions "pattern recognition" when discussing "sensory memory" and indicated that before encoding occurs, individuals will perceive the meaning of a stimulus and recognize what they see or hear (Chen, 2000). Therefore, "image" can be regarded as the comprehensive result of attitudes, thoughts, and impressions and serve as the foundation for the formation of attitudes, thoughts, and opinions. Image can also describe the characteristics or individual traits of people and government agencies (Chen, 2015a).

In previous election studies, scholars proposed research related to "candidate image." For instance, McGrath and McGrath (1962) posited that the theoretical concept of image is the personality traits projected by candidates to influence voters' perception to impact election results. Hahn and Gonchar (1972) explained that voters judge candidates based on their image, and their judgement is formed through the interaction of the voters' knowledge on the candidates' family background, personality traits, and values. Nimmo and Savage (1976) considered image as a type of mental construct comprising a combination of people, events, and objects that creates recognizable patterns. The concept of candidate image can be divided into two levels: a voter's subjective knowledge and the message that the candidate wishes to convey (Li, 2016). Bowes and Strentz (1978) noted that image is the psychological picture formed by the appearance and form received by voters from a candidate's message that reflect the various traits that the candidate wishes to convey.

By summarizing the basic definition of image, we can understand that image holds a significant place in people's perception and can influence their psychological feelings and cognitive choices. In modern political communication research, candidate image and communication media are closely related. Voters project their ideas, cognitions, and attitudes onto candidates and evaluate them based on their values, which in turn can affect their voting choices.

Positioning of candidate image

In recent years, candidates have concentrated on planning their marketing positioning and campaign strategies and utilizing mass communication tools to convey the image they wish to project. Various factors can influence voters' perception, with "party affiliation" being one of the most influential. The phenomenon of "Voting for the party, rather than the person" prevails in Taiwanese elections (Chuang, 2017). In addition, voters have become concerned about candidates' personal traits. For instance, a

candidate's ability to execute tasks, efficiency, integrity, honesty, understanding of their constituency and voters' needs, as well as their charisma and approachability, are factors that can influence voters' evaluation. By leveraging their personal traits, family background, and views on issues, candidates can find commonalities with voters, create resonance, and make voters feel that they share similar life experiences and can empathize with their struggles to increase their favorability (Cheng, 2014).

Mass media and social networking sites are voters' primary sources of information on candidates. Therefore, candidates shape their external image through campaign strategy planning and the use of media tools to market themselves. Thus, self-media on social networking sites plays a crucial role in recent election activities (Wang et al., 2019). Marketing a candidate is akin to marketing a product, in which "positioning" is vital. As a product on the campaign battlefield, candidates will encounter difficulties changing their political ideology, party affiliation, personality, or family background. However, understanding the inner world of voters, identifying their own uniqueness, and establishing relevance and resonance with the public are essential for candidates to gain voters' favor.

In candidate image positioning and brand impression shaping, aligning with contemporary events and contexts while matching their personality traits to establish a connection with voters is necessary for candidates. The approach can spark voters' interest and prompt them to pay attention to a candidate and help candidates earn their trust, which are the fundamental principle of candidate brand positioning (Shao, 2018). Voters care about candidates' ability to execute tasks, efficiency, integrity, honesty, understanding of their constituency and voters' needs, as well as their charisma and approachability. Hence, candidates can identify similarities with voters based on their personal traits, family background, and views on issues and make voters feel that they share similar life experiences and can empathize with their struggles to increase their favorability (Cheng, 2014). Hence, positioning candidates according to voters' preference is crucial.

Furthermore, domestic and international election models and recent academic studies revealed that online campaigns have emerged as important influencers. For instance, domestic candidates typically have Facebook fan pages and official LINE accounts, whereas international candidates typically use X. to garner public attention. After being elected, candidates continue to leverage the power of digital social media to announce relevant policies and collaborate with influencers to host livestreaming programs. Such a strategy can help attract different age groups to political figures' activities and allow the public to participate directly in and understand national policies clearly (Chiu, 2017).

A candidate's political platform is one of the key elements used by candidates to send messages to their voters and highlight their image. At the beginning of their campaign, regardless of whether they are young and well educated or come from a political family, new candidates are typically criticized by their rivals for lacking substance and experience. Therefore, communicating their political platform and gaining policy direction approval from voters are ways through which candidates can enhance their image. In summary, candidates can make a lasting impression on voters and garner public support by creating a differentiated brand image, utilizing a clear campaign theme, and communicating their policies effectively. A candidate's positioning and campaign strategy can determine their personal image and attract voters (2018).

Candidate image construction dimensions and criteria

In the literature on candidate image, apart from election strategies, five primary dimensions are identified as crucial indicators for assessing a candidate's image: family background, personal traits, party affiliation, electoral strategies and media relations.

Family Background. The phenomenon of “political inheritance” is prevalent in Taiwan. Many candidates who are unknown and running for office for the first time may have prominent political figures as parents or relatives. Such so-called “second-generation politicians” benefit from family resources, which can enable them to gain voter recognition quickly. However, their family background can also be a double-edged sword that can bring praise and criticism. During Taiwan’s ninth Legislative Yuan elections, more than half of the candidates with a political family background, whether through familial or marital connections, were elected. In addition, the proportion of the county and city councilors with a political family background reached 24.6%. Despite being largely unknown to the voters, such individuals had well-known family elders (2020).

The numbers indicate that nepotism and patronage are prevalent in grassroots elections, which were highly pronounced in the efforts of the Kuomintang (KMT) and Democratic Progressive Party (DPP) to win over such families. Hu (2017) pointed out that the current electoral system framework favors members of political families, which can entrench voters’ perception and make carving out their own path difficult for candidates. Regardless of a candidate’s chosen route, it will be seen as being aligned with their family’s ideology. Nonetheless, the family background of second-generation politicians continues to attract significant attention and discussion. Thus, being a second-generation politician can provide a distinct advantage to a candidate who is pursuing their political career.

Personal Traits. When a candidate’s family background fosters deeply ingrained stereotypes among voters, their personal traits will become essential for establishing a new path. Characteristics such as appearance, educational background, professional expertise, and personality can significantly shape a candidate’s image. In recent years, many new faces in politics are young and attractive, which can quickly draw media and voter attention. Titles such as “male god” and “goddess,” which are borrowed from the entertainment industry, are often used to describe such political newcomers. Young candidates typically possess high academic qualifications and address the issues avoided by older generation politicians, such as same-sex marriage, the unification–independence debate, and the pension reform. By addressing such issues, young politicians can reflect generational changes and attract young voters to pay attention to public issues and thus influence election outcomes. Therefore, contemporary candidates place significant emphasis on the youth vote. Candidates’ personal traits vary; some are sharp and assertive, whereas others are rational and gentle, with each having their own supporters. When candidates exhibit their personality traits in a way that resonates with voters, over time, their traits will constitute their unique image.

Party Affiliation. Election studies revealed that individuals’ background and upbringing will typically lead them to adopt their parents’ political preferences through family political socialization, which in turn will shape their national identity and party preference. Emotional attachment to a political party, which is known as “party identification,” is a crucial concept (Lin, 2019). Party identification can directly influence not only voters’ choices but also their views on issues and candidates and serve as a filter through which they interpret political information. Moreover, party identification is typically stable and enduring and resembles a lifelong commitment that rarely changes without the occurrence of significant events. Thus, when the majority of the populace demonstrates strong party identification, their attitude toward issues and voting behavior will reflect their affiliation and form the “base” of the electorate (Chen, 2015b).

Electoral Strategies. Recent political elections revealed that campaigns have evolved into a dynamic interplay between candidates, news media, and voters. The interaction of the three parties is akin to a symbiotic relationship, with each party depending on the others. Chou et al. (2017) noted

that democratic politics is a competitive process in which political elites employ various methods to establish their candidate image to garner votes. Common campaign strategies include using the media to disseminate information and inviting celebrities to endorse the candidates. Wang (2000) argued that mass media can significantly impact Taiwanese voters, particularly in the context of image construction. The internet and media in Taiwan are widespread and mature, and voters rely on the media to obtain information about candidates and acquire political knowledge. Meanwhile, candidates use the media to achieve their communication objectives, thereby underscoring the media's crucial role in the "golden triangle" of election campaigns.

Media Relations. Media presence is inevitable during elections, and a reciprocal influence relationship exists between politics and the media. Typically referred to as the "fourth estate," it serves as a societal tool for overseeing the government, politics, and social justice. The media is expected to provide comprehensive and trustworthy information and to facilitate rational and equitable dialogues to help citizens and the government clarify situations and make informed decisions. However, the media can overstep its boundaries and become a tool for political forces, acting as a mouthpiece for political actors and transforming into a propaganda machine. Hence, candidates strive to maintain good relations with the media and use media tools to disseminate favorable information (Wang, 2017).

In recent years, the new media battlefield has become a critical arena for candidates, and platforms such as Facebook, LINE, Instagram, and various fan pages have become essential. Candidates use social media to share their political views and ideas and often create promotional graphics to simplify complex texts and produce promotional videos for specific issues. Beyond social media promotion, candidates employ different media campaign techniques to promote their political views, such as launching an Instagram account and personal YouTube channels that feature various programs. The creation of different thematic videos to attract young audiences typically involves collaborating with influencers, which can foster candidates' interaction with fans and expand their voter base (Huang, 2019).

In this era of new media, the use of websites for broadcasting election news has become routine. Media outlets exert effort to attract voter clicks by creating dedicated election pages on their news platforms and integrating news, election data, and comprehensive analyses of different candidates' policies. Compared with traditional print newspapers, news websites, such as United Daily News, Liberty Times, and Apple Daily, offer more categories and integrate other poll data and multimedia sections. The web design of Liberty Times and Apple Daily is particularly eye catching. By contrast, though China Times Electronic News has an elections page, it has only basic related news categories (Lu, 2013).

Based on the literature review and description of the dimensions in the previous section, this study evaluates candidates' image across the five dimensions and 23 criteria presented in tables 1–3.

Table 1. Scholarly review of literature on candidate image construction and dimensions

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
Family background		X		X					
Personal traits	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
Party affiliation		X	X	X	X	X			
Electoral Strategies	X								X
Media relations	X		X	X	X			X	X

A. Wang (2000); B. Wu (2006); C. Lin (2001); D. Huang (1996); E. Pan (1998); F. Cheng et al. (2005); G. Patterson (1980); H. Hung (2008); I. Chen (2002a)

Table 2. Related literature on criteria for candidate image construction

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
Family background											
Affinal Relatives					X						
Parental Perspectives						X					
Spousal Perspectives					X						
Economic Circumstances						X					
Personal traits											
Physical Appearance								X			
Age	X			X							
Geopolitical Relations				X						X	
Educational Attainment	X			X		X					
Political Experience	X										
Party affiliation											
Political Party	X		X	X			X	X	X		
Regional Factions			X	X		X			X		
Intraparty Factions	X										
Political Network									X		
Strategic Voting Effect				X					X		X
Electoral strategies											
Political Platform							X				
Legislative Position	X		X	X			X				
Campaign Strategy	X		X		X						
Constituency Assistance Plan										X	
Constituent Case Services										X	
Media relations											
Media Image	X	X	X		X						
Media Exposure		X			X						
Interaction with Communities and Fans	X	X									
Public Opinion Poll								X			

A. Wang et al. (2019); B. Li (2016); C. (Chen, 2002b); D. Wu and Hsu (2003); E. Hsiao (2014); F. Su (2012); G. Liu (1996); H. Lin (2014); I. Hsu and Chen (2004); J. Lin (2005); K. Chang (2016)

Table 3. Description of candidate image construction criteria

Dimensions	Criteria	Definitions
A. Family background	A1. Affinal Relatives	Candidate's other family members with previous political experience or originating from a political family, commonly known as "second-generation politicians"; such a background can significantly influence a candidate's political career.
	A2. Parents' Political Experience	Candidate's parents with political experience, whose opinions exert a significant influence on the candidate
	A3. Spousal Political Experience	Candidate's spouse or in-laws with political experience, whose opinions significantly influence the candidate
	A4. Economic Circumstances	Candidate's socioeconomic status and industry in which they are employed; professional expertise and attitude toward labor relations

Dimensions	Criteria	Definitions
B. Personal traits	B1. Physical Appearance	Degree of attractiveness of a candidate's physical appearance or body features
	B2. Age	A candidate's age is regarded as a "generational struggle," which reflects the distinct political spectrum between young and old generations.
	B3. Geopolitical Relations	Geographical identification and interactive relationship between a candidate and their constituency
	B4. Educational Attainment	Candidate's educational background, which signifies their professional academic training; implies their high capacity for learning and knowledge acquisition
	B5. Political Experience	Candidate's experience in politics, which can give them a solid foundation and comprehension of administration, legislation, and local governance
C. Party affiliation	C1. Political Party	Political party represented by a candidate
	C2. Regional Factions	Close-knit communities where a candidate can create a political environment that cannot be easily created by nonmembers owing to their ethnic, clan, or geographical connections or blood relations or shared interests; examples include the Chen family faction in Taipei City; the Big Huang, the Small Huang, and the Liu factions in Miaoli County; and the Red, Black, and Yang factions in Taichung
	C3. Party Factions	Ebb and flow of individual factions within a candidate's political party; well-known factions within the DPP include the Formosa faction, the New Tide faction, the Justice Alliance
	C4. Political Network	Candidates who belong to certain grassroots organizations that serve to supplement their limited social network; examples include administrative agencies, farmers' and fishermen's associations, water conservancy associations, women's associations, and volunteer firefighter and police groups
	C5. Strategic Voting Effect	Strategic voting refers to a vote allocation method in which voters reluctantly concentrate their votes on the candidate with the best chance of winning to avoid splitting votes among candidates with similar positions or qualities.
D. Electoral strategies	D1. Political Platform	Candidate's political stance presented during elections to emphasize their main policies and make promises to achieve their goals, if elected
	D2. Legislative Position	Candidate's perspectives and opinions on contemporary social conditions, specific national political events, and particular issues, as well as leadership qualities
	D3. Campaign Strategy	Marketing and planning strategies for campaign activities used by candidates after analyzing shifts in the political environment
	D4. Constituency Assistance Plan	Candidate's efforts to secure various public infrastructure projects and funding subsidies from government departments for their constituency; examples include installation of streetlights; construction of parks, bridges, and public facilities; acquisition of welfare subsidies
	D5. Constituent Case Services	Assistance provided by candidates to individuals or specific groups to address their concerns with administrative departments; examples include attending weddings and funerals, managing personnel requests, and seeking redress for grievances

Dimensions	Criteria	Definitions
E. Media relations	E1. Media Image	Candidate's personal image as portrayed in traditional mass media, such as print newspapers and television news, as well as relevant election information provided to voters
	E2. Media Exposure	Candidate's exposure through news media, newspapers, magazines, and television to garner voter attention and increase their visibility; encompasses candidates' use of campaign materials, ranging from traditional newspapers and advertising flyers to television campaign ads and online media
	E3. Interaction with Communities and Fans	Candidate's use of social media and other self-media platforms to shape their personal image and establish an emotional connection with the public; candidates promote themselves by posting articles to enable voters to understand their values, commentary on current events, and political views to enhance their online presence
	E4. Public Opinion Poll	Polling is the analytical process of estimating election outcomes based on statistical data.

Methodology

This study employs the DANP method, which integrates the DEMATEL and ANP methods, to analyze the evaluation criteria that can influence candidates' image. In addition, this study conducts IPA to assess the appropriate management approaches for each criterion, which can establish the relationships between the criteria and identify the key criteria and thus provide a reference for candidates' image construction.

Application of combined DEMATEL and ANP (DANP) models

The DANP research method combines the DEMATEL and ANP methods. Specifically, the DEMATEL method developed by the Battelle Geneva Research Center was designed to solve complex problems by simplifying and systematizing them. The method entails the pairwise comparison of each criterion to determine its degree of influence, followed by mathematical matrix calculation to establish the causal relationships among all the criteria. The numerical values in the matrix indicate the strength of the criteria's mutual influence. The hierarchical structure method can aid in understanding special and complex problems and identifying core issues and improvement methods (Chu, 2016).

The ANP method proposed by Saaty (1996) is an improvement on the traditional AHP method and can be used to solve nonlinear and network-related problems, as well as issues with complex factor interrelationships. The DANP method employs the DEMATEL method to identify the interrelationships between the criteria and the ANP method to calculate their influence weight accurately to achieve the analytical objectives. The analytical process is divided into four steps ((Hu et al., 2015, Lee et al., 2009):

Step 1: Establish the problem structure, define the decision objectives, and create the network hierarchy framework.

Step 2: Construct the unweighted matrix, and calculate the influence relationship between the various factors by using the DEMATEL method to form the importance matrix.

Step 3: Calculate the total importance of each factor and normalize it to obtain the weighted supermatrix.

Step 4: Multiply the weighted supermatrix obtained in the previous step multiple times until it converges to the limit supermatrix.

Importance and Performance Analysis (IPA)

IPA is typically conducted in service quality research to assess customer evaluations of products and services to identify strategies that can enhance customer satisfaction. The method relies on two key metrics for the evaluation. The first metric is “importance,” which signifies the importance of a product or a service to a customer and is typically articulated as “expectation” or “importance.” The second key metric is “performance”, which reflects a customer’s perception of how effectively a product or a service meets their expectations and is generally expressed as “perception” or “satisfaction”.

IPA categorizes the two dimensions of “importance” and “performance” into four quadrants by using a graphical coordinate system. The approach visualizes the prioritization of the attributes related to products and services and their corresponding performance level. Martilla and James (1977) initially employed the framework to analyze products in the motorcycle industry and mapped product importance and performance onto four quadrants, with each quadrant representing distinct implications, as illustrated in Figure 1.

(1) Quadrant 1 - Attributes with high importance and high performance; attributes that fall within this quadrant should be maintained consistently (“keep up the good work”).

(2) Quadrant 2 - Attributes with low importance but high performance; attributes that fall within this quadrant suggest an oversupply situation (“possible overkill”).

(3) Quadrant 3 - Attributes with low importance and low performance, which imply low priority in ranking (“low priority”).

(4) Quadrant 4 - Attributes with high importance but low performance; attributes that fall into this quadrant should be the primary focus of suppliers’ improvement efforts.

Figure 1. IPA Diagram (Martilla and James, 1977)

<p>Quadrant 3 “Low priority”</p>	<p>Quadrant 2 “Possible overkill”</p>
<p>Quadrant 4 “Concentrate here”</p>	<p>Quadrant 1 “Keep up the good work”</p>

Research participants and data collection

This study selects a total of 23 participants, who are divided into two main groups: 10 current legislators and 13 aides with extensive experience in multiple election campaigns, strategic planning, and self-media and social media platform management. The participants represent a diverse range of political parties, political families, age groups, and election strategies. Table 4 presents the statistics of the legislators, and Table 5 details the statistics of the aides.

For the data collection, this study employs the “three-point scale” methodology of Hu et al. (2015) and Hu et al. (2017). The scale consists of three options to evaluate the degree of impact: no influence (0), slight influence (1), and definite influence (2). The approach is used to analyze the relevance of the various image criteria among the different candidates.

Table 4. Summary of educational and professional background of legislators and aides

Identifier	Gender	Education	Age	Political Affiliation	Marital status	Work experience
Legislators						
A	F	MA	60	KMT	Married	9 years
B	F	PhD	54	DPP	Married	4 years
C	M	MA	56	KMT	Married	1 year
D	F	MA	36	TPP	Single	7 years
E	F	MA	66	KMT	Married	1 year
F	F	BA	47	DPP	Married	5 years
G	M	MA	45	DPP	Married	5 years
H	M	BA	68	KMT	Married	18 years
I	M	PhD	48	KMT	Married	9 years
J	M	PhD	41	KMT	Married	5 years
Aides						
A	M	MA	50	KMT	Married	10 years
B	F	MA	55	KMT	Married	30 years
C	F	BA	31	KMT	Married	6 years
D	F	BA	24	NA	Single	2 years
E	M	BA	31	KMT	Single	5 years
F	M	BA	30	NA	Single	3 years
G	F	BA	35	DPP	Single	6 years
H	M	BA	28	DPP	Single	1 year
I	F	MA	33	DPP	Single	3 years
J	F	BA	30	KMT	Married	6 years
K	M	MA	37	KMT	Married	10 years
L	F	MA	32	KMT	Single	7 years
M	M	BA	35	KMT	Single	7 years

Notes: KMT – Kuomintang, DPP – Democratic Progressive Party, TPP – Taiwan People’s Party.

Analysis

This study consolidates the 23 criteria related to candidate image, as proposed by previous scholars. This study categorizes the criteria into five dimensions. Specifically, dimension A: “family background” consists of four criteria, dimension B: “personal characteristics” consists of five criteria, dimension C: “party identification” consists of five criteria, dimension D: “election strategy” consists of five criteria, and dimension E: “media relations” consists of four criteria. This study examines the interrelationships between the criteria that can influence candidate image from the perspective of the legislators and the campaign aides by using the DANP method. Table 3 details the dimensions and criteria.

DEMATEL causal influence

Comprehensive influence relationships – Legislators. This section analyzes the opinions of the experts in the field of political work, specifically, the perspectives of the ten legislators, to calculate the degree of influence and the degree of being influenced of the various dimensions and criteria and estimate their mutual influence relationships.

Among the DEMATEL evaluation indicators, degree of being influenced (d) represents the relationship between an element and the overall system, whereas the degree of influence (r) denotes the total strength of an element's impact on the other elements in the system. The calculation process involves compiling the data collected from the survey into a direct influence relationship matrix and normalizing and weighting the matrix to obtain the total influence relationship matrix. Summing each row of the matrix will yield the row sum (d), and summing each column will yield the column sum (r).

The importance (d+r) and cause (d-r) values, which are derived from the degree of being influenced (d) and the degree of influence (r), can be used to determine the strength of the influence of an element or the extent to which an element is influenced by the other elements. When the importance value (d+r) is greater than 0, the larger the value, the higher the importance, and the stronger the influence of the element in the overall system. By contrast, when the cause value (d-r) is less than 0, the larger the negative value, the higher the degree of influence of the other elements in the overall system on an element.

Table 5. Comprehensive influence relationships – Legislators

Dimension	Criteria	d		r		d+r		d-r	
		Degree of Being Influenced		Degree of Influence		Prominence		Relation	
A	A1	1.54	9.45	1.85	7.96	3.39	17.41	-0.31	1.50
	A2	1.86		1.67		3.53		0.19	
	A3	1.89		2.56		4.45		-0.67	
	A4	2.78		2.60		5.39		0.18	
B	B1	2.08	10.17	1.75	9.32	3.83	19.49	0.33	0.85
	B2	2.44		2.67		5.11		-0.24	
	B3	2.99		3.38		6.37		-0.38	
	B4	2.81		3.31		6.12		-0.49	
	B5	4.48		4.46		8.94		0.03	
C	C1	3.90	9.24	4.06	9.65	7.96	18.89	-0.16	-0.41
	C2	3.63		3.32		6.95		0.31	
	C3	3.41		3.49		6.90		-0.07	
	C4	3.88		3.97		7.85		-0.09	
	C5	3.04		2.64		5.68		0.40	
D	D1	4.09	9.66	3.98	10.35	8.07	20.01	0.11	-0.69
	D2	4.04		4.21		8.26		-0.17	
	D3	4.04		4.24		8.28		-0.19	
	D4	3.83		3.63		7.46		0.20	
	D5	3.69		3.62		7.31		0.07	
E	E1	4.38	8.98	4.06	10.22	8.44	19.20	0.33	-1.25
	E2	4.04		4.00		8.04		0.04	
	E3	3.87		3.27		7.14		0.60	
	E4	3.68		3.70		7.38		-0.01	

Table 5, which presents the analysis of the legislators’ opinions, reveals the comprehensive influence relationships. With regard to the importance value (d+r), dimension D: “election strategy” demonstrates the highest value, which indicates that, from the legislators’ perspective, dimension D exerts the strongest influence among all the dimensions in the overall system. By contrast, the cause value (d-r) reveals that dimension E: “media relations” has the lowest value, which suggests that the legislators generally perceive dimension E as being the most susceptible to the influence of the other factors. The criteria of the other dimensions for Legislators are illustrated in the causal diagram of the key criteria in the left panel of Figure 2, which is based on the magnitude of their values.

Figure 2. Causal relationships between key criteria – Legislators and Aides

Comprehensive influence relationships – Aides. This section analyzes candidate image from the perspective of the aides and incorporates the views of 13 individuals. By using the same methodology, this study calculates the degree of influence and the degree of being influenced of the dimensions and criteria and estimates their mutual influence relationship. The results are summarized in Table 6.

This table presents the analysis of the aides’ opinions, revealing the way they perceive the comprehensive influence relationships. For the importance value (d+r), dimension D: “election strategy” exhibits the highest value, which indicates that, from the aides’ perspective, dimension D exerts the strongest influence among all the dimensions in the overall system. By contrast, the cause value (d-r) reveals that dimension E: “media relations” has the lowest value, which suggests that the aides generally perceive dimension E as being the most susceptible to the influence of the other factors.

The criteria of the other dimensions, as indicated in Table 6, are illustrated in the causal diagram of the key criteria in the right panel of Figure 2.

Table 6. Comprehensive influence relationships – Aides

Dimension	Criteria	d		r		d+r		d-r	
		Degree of Being Influenced		Degree of Influence		Prominence		Relation	
A	A1	3.34	5.51	3.46	4.91	6.80	10.42	-0.13	0.59
	A2	3.65		3.69		7.34		-0.03	
	A3	3.95		3.59		7.54		0.36	
	A4	4.58		3.31		7.89		1.27	
B	B1	3.70	7.08	3.45	6.46	7.14	13.54	0.25	0.62
	B2	3.58		3.45		7.03		0.14	
	B3	3.52		4.56		8.08		-1.04	
	B4	3.40		3.44		6.84		-0.03	
	B5	5.52		5.52		11.04		-0.00	
C	C1	5.19	5.75	4.87	6.21	10.06	11.96	0.32	-0.461
	C2	4.38		4.88		9.27		-0.50	
	C3	4.46		4.63		9.09		-0.17	
	C4	5.01		4.42		9.43		0.59	
	C5	4.03		4.04		8.07		-0.01	
D	D1	4.80	6.76	5.18	6.99	9.97	13.75	-0.38	-0.24
	D2	4.87		5.30		10.17		-0.43	
	D3	5.34		5.59		10.92		-0.25	
	D4	4.99		5.05		10.05		-0.06	
	D5	5.11		4.80		9.90		0.31	
E	E1	5.53	6.00	5.56	6.52	11.09	12.52	-0.03-	-0.52
	E2	5.19		5.32		10.51		0.13	
	E3	4.84		4.02		8.86		0.83	
	E4	4.34		5.21		9.55		-0.87	

Importance and Performance Analysis (IPA)

Importance and Performance Analysis (IPA) can aid in identifying the criteria that require improvement. Table 7 presents the “rank sum” scores, in which the higher the performance score, the greater the self-satisfaction, and the higher the rank, the higher the importance. The performance can be assessed according to the Performance Value Evaluation Scale:

- Scores of up to 25 indicate very bad performance
- Scores between 26 and 50 indicate bad performance
- Scores between 51 and 70 indicate acceptable performance
- Scores between 71 and 85 indicate good performance
- Scores between 86 and 100 indicate very good performance.

This study determines the strengths and weaknesses of the candidates in relation to the specific performance criteria by conducting IPA. The analysis involves plotting the average importance and satisfaction values on a two-dimensional matrix. This study categorizes the attributes of the candidate image criteria into four quadrants: high importance–high satisfaction, high importance–low satisfaction, low importance–low satisfaction, and low importance–high satisfaction. The results are illustrated in Figure 3.

Table 7. Performance evaluation results

	Significance	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	Score	Rank
A. Family Background	A1. Affinal Relatives	50	60	90	50	70	70	100	30	80	50	65	23
	A2. Parents' Political Experience	10	80	80	50	30	50	70	30	50	30	48	22
	A3. Spousal Political Experience	80	80	70	50	80	70	100	60	80	80	75	20
	A4. Economic Circumstances	100	60	50	50	90	50	70	70	70	70	68	18
B. Personal Traits	B1. Physical Appearance	30	80	60	50	30	50	70	30	60	80	54	20
	B2. Age	50	60	90	40	30	60	50	50	60	80	57	19
	B3. Geopolitical Relations	50	90	80	80	50	50	90	80	50	60	68	15
	B4. Educational Attainment	50	100	80	40	50	50	80	60	80	90	68	17
	B5. Political Experience	100	80	70	30	80	80	70	90	90	70	76	1
C. Party Affiliation	C1. Political Party	80	80	60	30	80	80	100	90	80	70	75	7
	C2. Regional Factions	70	60	60	70	60	80	100	90	60	60	71	13
	C3. Party Factions	80	60	50	80	80	60	90	70	80	60	71	14
	C4. Political Network	30	100	70	80	80	70	70	80	80	80	74	8
	C5. Strategic Voting Effect	10	40	80	50	30	20	70	30	30	20	38	16
D. Electoral Strategies	D1. Political Platform	100	70	80	60	50	60	70	80	70	80	72	3
	D2. Legislative Position	100	70	90	40	60	80	90	80	70	80	76	4
	D3. Campaign Strategy	100	60	60	70	50	80	100	90	80	70	76	4
	D4. Constituency Assistance Plan	100	100	50	90	50	80	100	100	80	90	84	9
	D5. Constituent Case Services	100	90	50	100	70	80	90	90	90	80	83	12
E. Media Relations	E1. Media Image	100	90	50	70	60	60	70	70	90	90	75	2
	E2. Media Exposure	100	90	50	70	60	60	80	70	90	80	75	6
	E3. Interaction with Communities / Fans	100	90	60	30	80	70	70	60	80	80	72	10
	E4. Public Opinion Poll	100	80	80	80	30	50	90	50	50	60	67	10

The characteristics of the four quadrants and the corresponding management strategies are detailed below.

Quadrant 1 “Keep up the good work”. This quadrant encompasses the criteria that are highly important and highly satisfactory. The candidates should maintain and actively promote their performance in the criteria in this quadrant to solidify their competitive advantages.

Quadrant 2 “Possible overkill”. This quadrant encompasses the criteria that exhibit relatively low importance but high satisfaction. The results suggest that the criteria in the quadrant may be receiving excessive attention and being overdeveloped. Thus, resources should be reallocated from the criteria to the other critical image criteria for their improvement and enhancement.

Quadrant 3 “Low priority”. This quadrant encompasses the criteria that exhibit low importance and low satisfaction. The image criteria in this quadrant are relatively unimportant and can be prioritized for improvement after the high-priority criteria are addressed.

Quadrant 4 “Concentrate here”. This quadrant consists of the criteria that are highly important but exhibit low satisfaction. The image criteria in this quadrant should be prioritized by the candidates for immediate enhancement.

Figure 3. Performance evaluation

Discussion

Figure 3 shows that all the elements are situated within only three quadrants. The meaning of the placement of the criteria in each quadrant is detailed below.

The nine criteria classified in the first quadrant, namely, the “keep up the good work” quadrant, are “political experience (B5)”, “political party (C1)”, “political network (C4)”, “political platform (D1)”, “legislative position (D2)”, “campaign strategy (D3)”, “constituency assistance plan (D4)”, “media image (E1)”, and “media exposure (E2)”. The items are of paramount importance to voters and the aspects that the candidates diligently strive to maintain. The shared characteristics of the items are their public interest, accessibility, and media coverage. Therefore, campaign teams should not ignore the areas, they are crucial for maintaining the candidates’ voter base. The candidates should uphold

current standards, because lapses may be magnified and scrutinized and may directly damage their image.

The five criteria in the second quadrant, namely, the “possible overkill” quadrant, are “spousal political experience (A3)”, “regional factions (C2)”, “party factions (C3)”, “constituent case services (D5)”, and “interaction with communities and fans (E3)”. The results indicate that the candidates’ level of performance in the criteria surpasses their expected level of importance. The candidates have demonstrated strong performance in the criteria; thus, they can reallocate future resources to the other criteria that need improvement. The candidates should ensure that their performance in the criteria in this quadrant does not decline substantially.

The seven criteria in the third quadrant, namely, the “low priority” quadrant, are “affinal relatives (A1)”, “economic circumstances (A4)”, “physical appearance (B1)”, “age (B2)”, “geographical relations (B3)”, “educational attainment (B4)”, and “public opinion polls (E4)”. The results indicate that the candidates’ performance and perceived importance of the criteria are low. Thus, the criteria do not require immediate improvement, and priority should be given to the items in the third quadrant, which require urgent attention. Improvement of the criteria in the second quadrant should be pursued only when resources are ample. Over time, if resources permit, the enhancement of the image criteria may contribute to the overall increase in satisfaction with the candidates’ image.

Finally, the fourth quadrant, namely the “concentrate here” quadrant, does not include any criteria in our results. This study hypothesizes that the absence of criteria in this quadrant is due to the candidates’ awareness of the image criteria valued by modern voters. Thus, the candidates have exerted a concerted effort to strengthen the criteria, which has prevented significant performance discrepancies.

No items are classified under the “requires immediate improvement” quadrant, which can be attributed to the respondents’ diligence in maintaining their performance in the crucial areas to ensure voters’ satisfaction. Meanwhile, numerous items can be found under the “continued maintenance” quadrant, which must not be allowed to deteriorate and should be managed continuously with utmost care. The items categorized under the “no need to pay attention” quadrant are primarily related to the candidates’ family background, which cannot be altered through effort. Therefore, by leveraging their strengths, addressing their weaknesses, and performing consistently with their inherent conditions, candidates can deepen voters’ understanding.

Conclusion and recommendations

This study examines the relationships between 23 evaluation criteria based on the opinions of legislators and their staff on the candidates’ image. Figure 4 illustrates the convergence of the analysis results of the two groups. The essence of an election fundamentally revolves around whether voters identify with the candidate. The research data show that most of the legislators believe that their personal characteristics and family background are pivotal factors that can shape their image. Given their extensive election experience, the legislators comprehend the key to winning and possess a profound understanding of their strengths and personal image far more than their staff. The legislators know how to package themselves to attract voters’ attention. Although factors such as family background and age cannot be altered through personal effort, they can be packaged strategically to emphasize candidates’ unique advantages, such as highlighting the youth and vitality of young candidates and the stability and rich experience of old ones. Candidates can transform potential drawbacks into strengths by mastering such packaging techniques.

Figure 4. Intersection of image criteria between legislators and aides.

From the perspective of the staff members, designing the candidate image and packaging the candidate are an integral part of their role. Liu (2003) mentioned that election public relations, which are operated through political marketing models, are aimed primarily at “marketing” and “winning.” Therefore, media relations, family background, and party identification are important election strategy components. From the staff’s standpoint, amplifying the candidate’s image through media is crucial, thereby making media relations a key factor for attaining this goal.

Furthermore, the legislators and the staff members tend to agree on the criteria of the various dimensions and consider media image and political experience as critical criteria. Regarding media image, the candidates’ personal traits must be disseminated and managed through the media. Thus, whether a candidate’s image presented in the media aligns with their vision is crucial for their image construction. When the two elements align, the image construction will be successful; otherwise, adjustment will be necessary. However, for the candidates, shaping their media image requires support from their political party, public opinion polls, interactions with communities and fans, and news exposure. In other words, the other criteria have become a means for presenting a positive media image, with the core being how to align the candidate’s media image with their authentic image.

Regarding political experience, voters can discern a candidate’s personal characteristics and personality based on past experiences. Such understanding can be complemented by a candidate’s political views, district execution or planning, stance on issues, and campaign strategy decisions. The aspects are derived from the candidates’ prior political experience, and the identification of the suitable elements and packaging of the candidates’ previous choices in district construction or issue position can foster voters’ public identification with the candidates. The process can aid in shaping candidates’ image that aligns with the expectations of district voters.

Among the other criteria, news exposure is also crucial. As political figures, candidates’ professionalism is a key measure of their suitability. Therefore, for the staff members, shaping the candidate’s media image hinges on their news exposure. Positive professional news can create a favorable image for a candidate, whereas negative news exposure can damage a candidate’s image. Thus, managing positive news exposure is a secondary factor that can influence the media image criterion.

In conclusion, each candidate should leverage their unique characteristics. Catching voters' attention and interest would be a positive start. Once voters are willing to follow and invest considerable time in a candidate, the candidate will be able to convey their ideas. By utilizing image and packaging strategies, candidates can help voters gradually understand their political views and shape their image to align with voters' ideal candidate image to significantly increase their chances of getting votes.

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